

IDRisk – Digital Form Application

Field Test Summary Report

Version 1.2

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IDRisk

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1. Introduction

This document will present the results of the software field tests performed under the *IDRisk* project. This project was created with the main goal of developing a system of tools capable of providing field sampling technicians with a mobile platform which would facilitate the tasks of gathering food samples and all related sample information, while reducing occurrences of human error due to the high volume of data that has to be input, and also providing a more streamline way of relaying all the gathered information to the organization's data management system for later processing.

The developed platform, known and here on out referred as the *Digital Form Application*, contains an assortment of tools which were previously selected for two distinct testing scenarios: the first collection of tools was grouped together to be tested on a previous time frame to the day where the field test would occur. These tools were selected and used to prepare the sampling scenario where the sampling task would take place. These "setup" tools are an important part of the whole process, so it would make sense to have them be a part of the testing procedure; the second group of tools where the selected ones that would actually be used on the field via the technicians' mobile devices. These tools would receive inputs from the user related to the sample, ranging from simple text data up to photos taken and GPS coordinates of the location.

Additionally, it is important to note the type of platform that will be tested. The Digital Form Application is a web-based application hosted on a temporary development server with its own local database. This database currently holds all relevant data for development and testing, and later could be integrate with existing management systems. Having a web application that will be also accessed via mobile devices, such as smartphones, poses different challenges and require contrasting methodologies for testing when comparing to other types of applications, so special care was taken for the presented tests.

1.1 Overview

The ID Risk project, containing the Digital Form Application, is a proposal put together by several parties from different European Union (EU) member states: ASAE (Portugal), INSA (Portugal), LIACC (Portugal), and HAPIH (Croatia). The current document and tests described in it are related with the task of field testing the Digital Form Application in Portugal, as such, only 3 out of the 4 parties were involved in this test: ASAE, INSA and LIACC.

LIACC is the Artificial Intelligence and Computer Science Laboratory of the University of Porto, subcontracted by INSA to develop the web platform. LIACC was in charge of providing technical support in case the software had been presenting unexpected behaviors that would hinder the testing task.

Both ASAE and INSA had chosen a set of technicians with expertise in gathering food samples, and were in charge of testing the application. From ASAE two technicians were sent to two selected locations to both supervise and test the application. From INSA, three technicians were also sent to the same locations to use the application, however this

group also included an IT technician to assist the remaining personnel in case of a software failure on location and would request assistance from LIACC.

The following tables present a brief summary with the important details of the testing activity previously described.

Table 1 - Test Locations and Date

Test Location ID	Address	Establishment Type	Date of Testing
Location_1	Casal de Cambra, Sintra	Retailer	09/12/2021
Location_2	Casal de Cambra, Sintra	Retailer	09/12/2021

Table 2 - Test Participants

Tech. ID	Name	Organization	Role	Task Description	Test Location
SRT	Sidney Tomé	INSA	IT Support	Provide software support and guidance for the testing task	Location_1 & Location_2
FMR	Francisco Ravasco	INSA	Sampling	Perform tests as a user of the application by inserting sample data in the digital form	Location_1 & Location_2
???	Roberto Brazão	INSA	Sampling	Perform tests as a user of the application by inserting sample data in the digital form	Location_1 & Location_2
PMN	Pedro Nabais	ASAE	Supervisor	Monitor the test activity as well as the sample gathering process	Location_1 & Location_2
PJC	Paulo Carmona	ASAE	Sampling	Perform tests as a user of the application by inserting sample data in the digital form	Location_1 & Location_2
TS	Tiago Santos	LIACC	IT Developer	Provide solutions to problems that might occur on location and receive user feedback	N/A

2. Summary Assessment

Even though this report focusses on the field testing that took place on physical locations, as mentioned before in this document, planning and other previous testing were done in order to prepare for the field test, planning that was equally as important as the field test itself. For this reason, the following overall assessment describes two distinct scenarios performed on the same version of the platform. This is important to mention since issues and unexpected behaviors were found while executing the preparing phase, however since they didn't prevent the tests from executing from start to end, and while trying to fix those found issues would certainly create others' problems and consequently delay others tasks related to the project, we decided to move forward and test both scenarios under the same build of the platform, which was at the time version 0.1.

The following sections are a summary of the test case results obtained for the reported test effort. Refer to subordinate sections of this document for detailed results and explanations of any reported variances.

2.1 Preparing Scenario

Table 3 - Test Case Summary Results for the Preparing Scenario phase

Summary Assessment	Total Number of Test Cases	% of Total Planned	Comments
Test Cases Planned	24	100	Even though the Digital Form Application possesses many more features that could have been tested and included in the planning, they weren't essential for the Field Test, so these tests were planned only for the minimum required for the field test that would prove the usefulness of the application.
Test Cases Run	24	100	-
Test Cases Reviewed	24	100	-
Test Cases Passed	18	75	The majority of the tests planned passed which proved the robustness of the platform.
Test Cases Failed	6	25	Some functionalities that were deemed very important for the creation of the form and would affect how it would present on the field presented issues considered severe.
Test Cases to Be Run	0	0	-
Test Cases Held	0	0	-

The following is a summary of the test incidents (i.e., unexpected results, problems, and/or defects) that were reported during the testing:

Table 4 - Test Incident Summary Results

Impact/Severity Level	Total Reported	Total # Resolved	% Total Resolved	Total # Unresolved	% Total Unresolved
High Severity	4	4	100	0	0
Medium Severity	2	0	0	2	100
Combined Totals	6	4	66	2	33

2.2 Testing on Field

Table 5 - Test Case Summary Results for the Field Test

Summary Assessment	Total Number of Test Cases	% of Total Planned	Comments
Test Cases Planned	12	100	<i>These selected tests, once performed, would dictate whether the application could successfully or not perform its main goal.</i>
Test Cases Run	12	100	-
Test Cases Reviewed	12	100	-
Test Cases Passed	12	100	-
Test Cases Failed	0	0	-
Test Cases To Be Run	0	0	-
Test Cases Held	0	0	-

For the field test no incidents were reported. Every test that was planned presented the expected results with every single one being successful.

3. Detailed Test Results

For these tests we employed two type of testing processes: system acceptance testing and user acceptance testing.

The following table summarizes the test cases employed for the first scenario of planning performed the tests on the field.

Table 6 – Preparing phase Test Results

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Creation of a New Form	Using an admin account, use the Form Manager to create a new Form	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Editing existing Form	From an existing Form created in the Form Manager, select the option to Edit the target Form	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Add new Field Objects to a Form	From an existing Form previously created, have that Form be in edit mode and add some Field Objects to it	08/12/2021	Fail (Solved)	When adding a new Field to the Form page area, the field object would sometimes not appear, or appear in incorrect location. This issue was then solved.
Edit existing Field Objects on a Form	From an existing Form previously created, select an existing Field Object and have its properties edited	08/12/2021	Fail (Solved)	When editing some properties like position and width or height, the values inserted for those properties wouldn't correctly change the Field Object. This issue was also fixed.
Remove existing Field Objects on a Form	From an existing Form previously created, select an existing Field Object and remove it from the Form page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Position Field Object based on the grid system	From an existing Form previously created, select an existing Field Object and position it with the different grid alignment options	08/12/2021	Fail (Solved)	Sometimes when positioning the object, that object would not take in to account the grid definitions and be positioned incorrectly. This issue was also fixed.

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Group Field Objects together	From an existing Form previously created, select multiple objects on the page and select the option "Group"	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Text Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert Text field and input some values to it on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Numeric Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert Numeric field and input some values to it on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Date Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert Date field and input some values to it on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Text Area Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert Text Area field and input some values to it on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Image Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert Image field and have an image applied to it on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test GPS Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert GPS field and input some values to it on the Preview Page	08/12/2021	Fail	For some reason that we weren't able to fix before the field test, the coordinates weren't showing up on the page. Later to the testing this issue was solved.
Insert and test Radio Button Fields	From an existing Form previously created, insert Radio Button fields and check their behavior on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Insert and test CheckBox Fields	From an existing Form previously created, insert CheckBox fields and check their behavior on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Signature Field	From an existing Form previously created, insert Signature field and input some values to it on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Section Area	From an existing Form previously created, insert Section Area and check its appearance on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Required Fields event	From an existing Form previously created, define some fields to be "Required" and test this restriction on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert and test Table Queries	From an existing Form previously created, upload some table file containing some data. Create a Table query that would read and display that data on some fields. Test these functionalities on the Preview Page	08/12/2021	Fail	Due to a bug, the table file wasn't being uploaded to the server to be then read. This issue was later fixed, after the field test occurred.
Insert and test Header section	From an existing Form previously created, insert a header section with some fields in it check its appearance on the Preview Page	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Preview an existing Form	Using an admin account, go to the Form Manager and select an existing form to be previewed via the option "Preview"	07/12/2021	Pass	Sometimes the Designer application takes longer than expected. However, it manages to load the form without a problem.

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Testing preview in "Form View"	From the preview page, select the option "Form View" and check the Form appearance and layout	07/12/2021	Fail (Solved)	The elements present on the preview page where sometimes displayed in the incorrect location and sometimes their formatting was also incorrect. This problem was promptly fixed.
Testing preview in "List View"	From the preview page, select the option "List View" and check the Form appearance and layout	07/12/2021	Pass	-
Close and set existing Form as "Ready to be Used"	From the Form Manager, select an existing Form and select the option "Lock Form and Ready To Use"	07/12/2021	Pass	-

The following table summarizes the test cases employed for the second scenario consisting on the field test where the application was tested in the available mobile devices. It is important to mention that the inspectors testing the application will be inputting the same values that the inspector's performing the actual sampling task so the experience could be easily compared.

Table 7 – Field test phase Test Results

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Access the Inspector's App	With a user account, access to the Inspector's App via the given URL or installed application	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Access the created Form for Testing	Once in the Inspector's App, select the current Operation and open the created Form	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Inserting Text values to Text fields	Within the Form, insert text values to the available Text Fields	09/12/2021	Pass	-

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Inserting Numeric values to Numeric fields	Within the Form, insert numeric values to the available Numeric Fields	09/12/2021	Pass	Some fields had some incorrect maximum values which were the default values. This wasn't a bug or problem with the application, it was only that was missed when the Form was created and easy to correct.
Inserting the Date value to Date fields	Within the Form, insert the required dates to the available Date Fields	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Perform the selection of values using the Radio Buttons	Within the Form, use the available Radio Buttons to select the correct values	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Perform the selection of values using the CheckBox Buttons	Within the Form, use the available CheckBox Buttons to select the correct values	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Take picture of a sample	Within the application, select the option and take a picture of the sample	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Attach picture of sample to the Form	Within the Form, attach the picture that was previously taken from the sample, and upload it to the server	09/12/2021	Pass	-
Insert signature on the Signature Field	Within the Form, draw a signature on the Signature Field	09/12/2021	Pass	This feature responded better when using the finger instead of using a smartphone pen.
Test the validation of required field	Within the Form, once all values have been inputted, validate the form and check if the expected rules are being presented	09/12/2021	Pass	-

Test Case/Script ID	Test Case/Script Description	Date Tested	Pass/Fail	Comments
Finish the operation	Within the Form, save and close the form, signaling this way that operation has ended	09/12/2021	Pass	Right after the operation was deemed closed, the operator or any administrator could see the new status of the operation and have access to all data for additional validation.

4. Conclusions

It was found that the planning of tests to be performed prior the day of the field testing was crucial to the overall performance and behavior of the application. Throughout the development, whenever a new feature was developed, tests were constantly being done. However, we saw the need to perform a batch of testing to the application as a whole before going physically to the field and test the user front of the application. Thanks to this prior planning and testing phase, the field test experience presented great results and the tests themselves were executed effortlessly without any complications. The team was able to follow along without any problems the other technicians performing the sampling.

The team was very pleased with the results, especially with the field testing where all the test cases passed without an issue, overall we were expecting to find some problems but all of them were dealt with and fixed, allowing us to see and demonstrate on a very close to real scenario the advantages of using such platform.